

UD report

Kilu von Prince

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This is a report on the typological stratification of UD corpora at the time of writing.

- The list of UD corpora was downloaded from <https://universaldependencies.org/>. A total of 169 languages are currently represented by one or more corpora. These are already assigned to language families.
- I manually added ISO codes. I often had to guess ISO codes because they were not provided in the corpus description.
- Some obsolete languages, like Akkadian, do not have an ISO code.
- Three corpora record code switching between two or more languages. No ISO code was assigned and they did not show up in subsequent analyses.
- Twenty-six languages are represented by corpora smaller than 1k tokens. These were left out of the Vitality study because their corpus size could not be mapped.
- Based on ISO codes, I added number of speakers and EGIDS scores from <https://www.ethnologue.com/>.
- Also based on ISO codes, I added coordinates from <https://glottolog.org/>.
- These data are generally not available for obsolete languages. The seventeen obsolete languages in the sample do therefore not show up in the rest of the report¹
- A remaining total of 123 languages was analyzed for areal distribution and vitality. Families were analyzed for all 169 languages.

¹Akkadian, Ancient Greek, Ancient Hebrew, Classical Armenian, Classical Chinese, Coptic, Egyptian, Gothic, Hittite, Latin, Middle French, Old Church Slavonic, Old East Slavic, Old French, Ottoman Turkish, Phrygian, Sanskrit.

1 Areal distribution

According to glottolog, 2023 out of 8605 languages/langoids are spoken in Eurasia, so about 24%. By contrast, the majority of UD languages is spoken in Eurasia, especially in Europe, as illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Areal distribution of UD languages, with color indicating language family.

2 Family relations

Roughly 6% of languages belong to the Indo-European family, which is one of 430 families counted by glottolog. In the UD sample of 169 languages, 77 are Indo-European (IE), thus making up around 46% of the sample. The full list of families and their representation in the collection is illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Number of languages representing different language families.

3 Sociolinguistic properties

Languages differ widely in terms of EGIDS scores (Lewis & Simons, 2010) and the size of speaker populations. According to Ethnologue (Eberhard *et al.*, 2021), the vast majority of languages has an EGIDS score of five or lower, and less than one million speakers. By contrast, 80 out of 123 languages for which we can obtain these numbers, have an EGIDS score higher than five. In particular, bigger corpora are almost exclusively available for languages with a high EGIDS score. This is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: Size of speaker population and EGIDS scores of languages represented by corpora. The size of the circle indicates the corpus size.

References

- Eberhard, David M., Simons, Gary F., & Fennig, Charles D. (eds). 2021. *Ethnologue: Languages of the world*. 24 edn. Dallas, Texas: SIL International. Online version: <http://www.ethnologue.com>.
- Lewis, M Paul, & Simons, Gary F. 2010. Assessing endangerment: expanding fishman's gids. *Revue roumaine de linguistique*, 103–120.